

Additional File 1: Sequence alignment and SNP analysis of *LdMT* gene in LD843 strain (*LdMT_M*) with wild type sequence (*LdMT_W*)

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LdMT_M      ATGCCCAACCAACCGCCGTGTTGGCGCAAGTGCCTTTCCACCAGAATCTTCCCAGACAAG 60
LdMT_W      ATGCCCAACCAACCGCCGTGTTGGCGCAAGTGCCTTTCCACCAGAATCTTCCCAGACAAG 60
*****

LdMT_M      CTCTCCAAGTCCTTCTGCTGCTTTAGCGCAGAGGCGGACGTGGACGAGGATGATGTGGTG 120
LdMT_W      CTCTCCAAGTCCTTCTGCTGCTTTAGCGCAGAGGCGGACGTGGACGAGGATGATGAGGTG 120
*****

LdMT_M      ATCGTGTACCTTAAACGACCCCGAGTTGAACGCGCAGTTTAATTATCCGTCGAACTTCATT 180
LdMT_W      ATCGTGTACCTTAAACGACCCCGAGTTGAACGCGCAGTTTAATTATCCGTCGAACTTCATT 180
*****

LdMT_M      CGTACCTCCAAGGACACACTCATCTCCTTCCCTCCCACTCAGCCTCCTGTTGGAGTTCAA 240
LdMT_W      CGTACCTCCAAGTACACACTCATCTCCTTCCCTCCCACTCAGCCTCCTGTTGGAGTTCAA 240
*****

LdMT_M      AAGGTGAGTAATTTGTATTTTCTCATGAACGTCATATTCAGCCTCATCCCAAGTGTGTCC 300
LdMT_W      AAGGTGAGTAATTTGTATTTTCTCATGAACGTCATATTCAGCCTCATCCCAGGTGTGTCC 300
*****

LdMT_M      CCGCTAAGTCCGGCGACCTCGATTGCGCCGCTGTCCTTTGTGCTCATCGTGGCACTCATC 360
LdMT_W      CCGCTAAGTCCGGCGACCTCGATTGCGCCGCTGTCCTTTGTGCTCATCGTGGCACTCATC 360
*****

LdMT_M      AAGGAGGGGGTGGAGGACATCAAGCGACATCAGGCCGACAACCGCGCCAACTCGATTTTA 420
LdMT_W      AAGGAGGGGGTGGAGGACATCAAGCGACATCAGGCCGACAACCGCGCCAACTCGATTTTA 420
*****

LdMT_M      GTGCAGGTAACTGCGAAACGGCAAGCTCGTCTCGGTGCACAGCAAGGACATCCACCCTGGT 480
LdMT_W      GTGCAGGTAACTGCGAAACGGCAAGCTCGTCTCGGTGCACAGCAAGGACATCCACCCTGGT 480
*****

LdMT_M      GACGTCATGCGTATCAAGAACGGCGAGGAGGTGCGCGCCGATGTCGTCATGCTCGCCTCG 540
LdMT_W      GACGTCATGCGTATCAAGAACGGCGAGGAGGTGCGCGCCGATGTCGTCATGCTCGCCTCG 540
*****

LdMT_M      TCCGTCGAGGAAGGACAGGCATTTATAGACACATGTAACCTGGACGGCGAGACGAACCTG 600
LdMT_W      TCCGTCGAGGAAGGACAGGCATTTATAGACACATGTAACCTGGACGGCGAGACGAACCTG 600
*****
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LdMT_M AAGTCGCGCAAGGCTCTGGAAGCCACCTGGGCGCTCTGCGAAGTCGAGGCAATCATGAAT 660
LdMT_W AAGTCGCGCAAGGCTCTGGAAGCCACCTGGGCGCTCTGCGAAGTCGAGGCAATCATGAAT 660

LdMT_M AGCACAGCCGTACTGCACACGAGCAAGCCAGACCCAGGGTTGCTGTCTGTTGGGCAGGGCTG 720
LdMT_W AGCACAGCCGTACTGCACACGAGCAAGCCAGACCCAGGGTTGCTGTCTGTTGGGCAGGGCTG 720

LdMT_M TTGGAAATCAATGGCGAGGAGCACGCTCTCTCGCTGAACCAGTT**T**CTGTATCGCGGCTGC 780
LdMT_W TTGGAAATCAATGGCGAGGAGCACGCTCTCTCGCTGAACCAGTT**C**CTGTATCGCGGCTGC 780

LdMT_M GTGT**G**ACGCAACACGGACTGGGTGTGGGGCATGGTTGCCTACGCAGGGGTCGACACGAAG 840
LdMT_W GTGT**T**ACGCAACACGGACTGGGTGTGGGGCATGGTTGCCTACGCAGGGGTCGACACGAAG 840

LdMT_M CTGTTCCGAAACTTGAAGCCAAAACCGCCAAAGTCGTGCAACCTCGACCGCAAGCTGAAC 900
LdMT_W CTGTTCCGAAACTTGAAGCCAAAACCGCCAAAGTCGTGCAACCTCGACCGCAAGCTGAAC 900

LdMT_M TACTTTATCATAGCC**G**TCCTCATATTCCAGAACATCATGCTCTTCATCTTAGCCTCCATG 960
LdMT_W TACTTTATCATAGCC**A**TCCTCATATTCCAGAACATCATGCTCTTCATCTTAGCCTCCATG 960

LdMT_M GCAGTGTGGTGGAAACAGCAAGTACCGGGAAACGCCCTACCTCCGCTTCTTTATCAGCTTT 1020
LdMT_W GCAGTGTGGTGGAAACAGCAAGTACCGGGAAACGCCCTACCTCCGCTTCTTTATCAGCTTT 1020

LdMT_M CGCAAGAACG**C**AACTCTGTGGGGATAACCGCTACTTGAGTT**T**CTTCATTTTGCTGAGCTAC 1080
LdMT_W CGCAAGAACG**T**AACTCTGTGGGGATAACCGCTACTTGAGTT**A**CTTCATTTTGCTGAGCTAC 1080

LdMT_M TGCGTGCCCATCTCGCTGTTTCATCACGATTGAAGTGTGCAAAGTGGTCCAGGCGCAGTGG 1140
LdMT_W TGCGTGCCCATCTCGCTGTTTCATCACGATTGAAGTGTGCAAAGTGGTCCAGGCGCAGTGG 1140

LdMT_M ATGCGGGTGGACTGCCTCATGATGGAGTACATGAGCAACCGCTGGCGGCACTGCCAGCCG 1200
LdMT_W ATGCGGGTGGACTGCCTCATGATGGAGTACATGAGCAACCGCTGGCGGCACTGCCAGCCG 1200

LdMT_M AACACGTCGAACCTCAACGAGCAGCT**C**GCAATGGTGCCTTCATCTTCAGCGACAAAAC 1260
LdMT_W AACACGTCGAACCTCAACGAGCAGCT**A**GCAATGGTGCCTTCATCTTCAGCGACAAAAC 1260

LdMT_M GGGACGCTGACAGAGAACGTCATGAAGTTTAAAGCTAGGCGACGCTCTCGGTAATCCGATC 1320
LdMT_W GGGACGCTGACAGAGAACGTCATGAAGTTCAAGCTAGGCGACGCTCTCGGTAATCCGATC 1320

LdMT_M GACGCCGACAATCTGGACGAGTGCATCGCGCAGCTGCGCAAGGAGGCCGAGTCGAAGGGG 1380
LdMT_W GACGCCGACAATCTGGACGAGTGCATCGCGCAGCTGCGCAAGGAGGCCGAGTCGAAGGGG 1380

LdMT_M CTAGGCCCGCTGCAAGAGTACTTTCTCGCGCTGGCCCTGTGCAACACGGTTCAGCCCTTC 1440
LdMT_W CTAGGCCCGCTGCAAGAGTACTTTCTCGCGCTGGCCCTGTGCAACACGGTTCAGCCCTTC 1440

LdMT_M AAGGACGACACGGATGACTTGGGTGTTGTCTACGAAGGCAGCTCCCCAGACGAGGTGGCG 1500
LdMT_W AAGGACGACACGGATGACTTGGGTGTTGTCTACGAAGGCAGCTCCCCAGACGAGGTGGCG 1500

LdMT_M CTGGTCGAGACCGCTGCTGCTGTGGCTATCGCCTCATCAGCCGTACGACAAAGTCCATC 1560
LdMT_W CTGGTCGAGACCGCTGCTGCTGTGGCTATCGCCTCATCAGCCGTACGACAAAGTCCATC 1560

LdMT_M ACGTACTCCTGCACGATGGGACGCGCAAGGTATAACAACATCCTCGCCACACTGGAGTTC 1620
LdMT_W ACGTACTCCTGCACGATGGGACGCGCAAGGTATAACAACATCCTCGCCACACTGGAGTTC 1620

LdMT_M ACGCCGGACCGCAAGATGATGAGCATCATCGTCGAGGACAGCGACACCAAAAAAATTACG 1680
LdMT_W ACGCCGGACCGCAAGATGATGAGCATCATCGTCGAGGACAGCGACACCAAAAAAATTACG 1680

LdMT_M CTGTACAATAAGGGGGCCGACAGTTTCATCAGGCCGCAGCTGAGCCGCGCCCCGGATGTG 1740
LdMT_W CTGTACAATAAGGGGGCCGACAGTTTCATCAGGCCGCAGCTGAGCCGCGCCCCGGATGTG 1740

LdMT_M CAGGGGCACATCGAAAATGTCGAGATCCCTCTGACGGAAATGTCCTCGTCGGGGCTCCGC 1800
LdMT_W CAGGGGCACATCGAAAATGTCGAGATCCCTCTGACGGAAATGTCCTCGTCGGGGCTCCGC 1800

LdMT_M ACGCTGCTTGTGTGCGCCAAGGAAATCACACGGCGCCAGTTCGACCCATGGTTCGAGAAG 1860
LdMT_W ACGCTGCTTGTGTGCGCCAAGGATATCACACGGCGCCAGTTCGACCCATGGTTCGAGAAG 1860

LdMT_M TTCGTGCAAGCCGGCAAGTCCCTGCACAACCGCAGCTCCAATATTGTTAAAGTCTGCTTA 1920
LdMT_W TTCGTGCAAGCCGGCAAGTCCCTGCACAACCGCAGCTCCAATATTGATAAAAGTCTGCTTA 1920

LdMT_M GAGATGGAGCAAGATATGCGGCTCGTCGGTGCCACCGCTATCGAGGACAAGCTGCAAGAC 1980
LdMT_W GAGATGGAGCAAGATATGCGGCTCGTCGGTGCCACCGCTATCGAGGACAAGCTGCAAGAC 1980

LdMT_M GAGGTC CCTGAGACACTGTCCTTCTTCTTGAGCGCCGGTGTATCATTGGATGCTCACT 2040
LdMT_W GAGGTC CCTGAGACACTGTCCTTCTTCTTGAGCGCCGGTGTATCATTGGATGCTCACT 2040

LdMT_M GGCGACAAGCGCGAGACCGCCGTGACGATCGCTGCAACGTCGACCCTGTGCGACCCGCGC 2100
LdMT_W GGCGACAAGCGCGAGACCGCCGTGACGATCGCTGCAACGTCGACCCTGTGCGACCCGCGC 2100

LdMT_M AACGACTTCATCGACCACATCGACATTGGTCATCTGAATTCATCGGATCCCAAGGCGATT 2160
LdMT_W AACGACTTCATCGACCACATCGACATTGGTCATCTGAATTCATCGGATCCCAAGGCGATT 2160

LdMT_M GAGCGCGTAGGGCGCGACCTCGAAGTGGTGGAGCAGCACATCGCGCTCAAGGGGACCCAC 2220
LdMT_W GAGCGCGTAGGGCGCGACCTCGAAGTGGTGGAGCAGCACATCGCGCTCAAGGGGACCCAC 2220

LdMT_M AAGGAGCGGCGCTGCACCTTGGTCATCGACGGCCAGCGCTGAACATCGCAATGGAGCAC 2280
LdMT_W AAGGAGCGGCGCTGCACCTTGGTCATCGACGGCCAGCGCTGAACATCGCAATGGAGCAC 2280

LdMT_M TACTTTGACCAGTTCCTGCGCCTCTCCCATCAGGTCAACTCCGCCGTCTGCTGTCGTCTC 2340
LdMT_W TACTTTGACCAGTTCCTGCGCCTCTCCCATCAGGTCAACTCCGCCGTCTGCTGTCGTCTC 2340

LdMT_M ACGCCGATCCAGAAGGCAACCGTCGTTTCGCATGTTCCAGAAGTCAACCGGTAAGACAGCG 2400
LdMT_W ACGCCGATCCAGAAGGCAACCGTCGTTTCGCATGTTCCAGAAGTCAACCGGTAAGACAGCG 2400

LdMT_M CTGGCCATCGGTGACGGCGCCAACGACGTGTCCATGATCCGGGAGGGGCGTGTGGGCGTG 2460
LdMT_W CTGGCCATCGGTGACGGCGCCAACGACGTGTCCATGATCCGGGAGGGGCGTGTGGGCGTG 2460

LdMT_M GGCATTATTGGGCTGGAAGGTGCACACGCCGCCCTCGCCGCCGACTACGCGATTCCGCGG 2520
LdMT_W GGCATTATTGGGCTGGAAGGTGCACACGCCGCCCTCGCCGCCGACTACGCGATTCCGCGG 2520

LdMT_M TTCAAGCACCTGCGCCGCCTATGCGCGGTGCATGGCCGCTACTCGCTCTTCCGCAACGCC 2580
LdMT_W TTCAAGCACCTGCGCCGCCTATGCGCGGTGCATGGCCGCTACTCGCTCTTCCGCAACGCC 2580

LdMT_M AGCTGCATTCTGGT**C**AGCTTCCACAAGAACA**G**TACTGTGTCGGTGGTGCAGTTCATCTTC 2640
LdMT_W AGCTGCATTCTGGT**T**AGCTTCCACAAGAACA**T**TACTGTGTCGGTGGTGCAGTTCATCTTC 2640

LdMT_M GCCTTCTACGTCGGCTTCTCGGGGCTAACACTCTTTGATGGATGGATGCTGACCTTCTAC 2700
LdMT_W GCCTTCTACGTCGGCTTCTCGGGGCTAACACTCTTTGATGGATGGATGCTGACCTTCTAC 2700

LdMT_M AACGTCCTTCTAACAAGTATCCCACCCTTCTTCATGGGTATATTTCGATAAGGACCTCCCC 2760
LdMT_W AACGTCCTTCTAACAAGTATCCCACCCTTCTTCATGGGTATATTTCGATAAGGACCTCCCC 2760

LdMT_M GAAGATGCCCTGCTGGAGCGGCCGAAGCTGTACAC**C**CCGTTGTCGCATGGCGAGTACTTT 2820
LdMT_W GAAGATGCCCTGCTGGAGCGGCCGAAGCTGTACAC**A**CCGTTGTCGCATGGCGAGTACTTT 2820

LdMT_M AACCTGGCGACGCTTCTGCGGTGGTTCGTCAATCACTAACAACAGCGGTGATCCTCTTC 2880
LdMT_W AACCTGGCGACGCTTCTGCGGTGGTTCGTCAATCACTAACAACAGCGGTGATCCTCTTC 2880

LdMT_M TATGCTGCTTACCCGACATTGATCCGTCAAGACGGTTCCCATCAGCGCT**T**CACCGGCGGC 2940
LdMT_W TATGCTGCTTACCCGACATTGATCCGTCAAGACGGTTCCCATCAGCGCT**A**CACCGGCGGC 2940

LdMT_M GAGACCGGCACGCTCGTGTTTCAGCGGCTTGATCCTCGTCATTCAAACCTCGCTTCATCCTG 3000
LdMT_W GAGACCGGCACGCTCGTGTTTCAGCGGCTTGATCCTCGTCATTCAAACCTCGCTTCATCCTG 3000

LdMT_M CAGATCCGCTACTGGCAGTGGCTGCAGGTGTTTGGCATGGCGATGTCGATTTTTCTCTTT 3060
LdMT_W CAGATCCGCTACTGGCAGTGGCTGCAGGTGTTTGGCATGGCGATGTCGATTTTTCTCTTT 3060

LdMT_M CTGTTGTTGTTTCTCGTCTACTCCGCCATTCCCTCAGTCTTCAGTGACACGAATTT**G**AC 3120
LdMT_W CTGTTGTTGTTTCTCGTCTACTCCGCCATTCCCTCAGTCTTCAGTGACACGAATTT**T**AC 3120

LdMT_M TACCAAGCCTTCGATCTCATGTGCGACCGCCAAGTACTGGTTTTTCTGCTCCTCTACGTT 3180
LdMT_W TACCAAGCCTTCGATCTCATGTGCGACCGCCAAGTACTGGTTTTTCTGCTCCTCTACGTT 3180

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LdMT_M      GGCACCGAGGTGGTGGTCGTACTCGGCGTCATGACGTTCCAGAAGAACCTCTACCCTACC 3240
LdMT_W      GGCACCGAGGTGGTGGTCGTACTCGGCGTCATGACGTTCCAGAAGAACCTCTTCCCTACC 3240
*****
LdMT_M      CTGCGCGACGTCGCGGAGCGACAGTACGCTGTTCAAACGGTGGAAAGCTGTGA 3294
LdMT_W      CTGCGCGACGTCGCGGAGCGACAGTACGCTGTTCAAACGGTGGAAAGCTGTGA 3294
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Note: The alignment of nucleotide sequence (LD-843 strain) shows complete variants/SNPs obtained from Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV). The validated /significant SNPs are highlighted as green colour (Synonyms SNPs), red colour (non-synonyms SNPs) and yellow colour (other non-significant SNPs).